

A METHODOLOGY FOR G-CONTROLLED FATIGUE CHARACTERIZATION OF SANDWICH FACE/CORE INTERFACES USING THE MMB AND MODIFIED TSD SPECIMENS

C. Berggreen^{1*}, M. Manca¹, G. Paladini¹, A. Quispitupa¹ and L.A. Carlsson²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Nils Koppels Allé, Building 403, DK-2800 Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

² Department of Ocean and Mechanical Engineering, Florida Atlantic University, 777 Glades Road, Boca Raton, FL 33431, USA

* Corresponding author (cbe@mek.dtu.dk)

Keywords: *Sandwich composites, fracture toughness, mixed mode bending (MMB), tilted sandwich debond (TSD), fatigue debond crack growth*

1. Abstract

The current study focuses on the development of a methodology to perform fatigue crack growth characterization of debonded sandwich composites under well controlled cyclic energy release rate and mode-mixity. The proposed methodology exploits two different types of specimens and test techniques: the modified Tilted Sandwich Debond (TSD) and the Mixed Mode Bending (MMB) specimens. The crack length measurements are based on finite element analysis for the TSD specimens and on analytical compliance expressions for the MMB. Accurate fatigue crack growth measurements and better control of loading conditions at the crack tip using the modified TSD and the MMB test methods in combination with a G-control test algorithm for cyclic testing will be the outcomes from this work.

2. Introduction

Debonds in sandwich structures may be caused by poor bonding and careless manufacturing of sandwich components or by accidental impact loading of the structure during its lifetime. Debonds in sandwich structures are generally subjected to both static and/or cyclic loads, and debonds can cause a reduction in the load bearing capacity of the structure exposed to such loads, since tensile and shear loads cannot be transferred efficiently between core and the face sheets. As a result the overall strength and fatigue lifetime of the sandwich structure is compromised and in the worst case

scenario, catastrophic failures can occur. Most of the fatigue crack growth studies are based on load and displacement control and lead respectively to an increase or decrease of the energy release rate during the cyclic crack growth propagation. Therefore, the aim of the current study is to propose a consistent methodology to measure fatigue crack growth behavior in debonded sandwich specimens under well controlled mixed mode loading conditions and energy release rate. To this end, the MMB and the modified TSD sandwich specimens and test rigs will be employed.

3. The G-controlled methodology

The crack growth rate in foam-cored sandwich structures is correlated to the applied cyclic energy release rate amplitude ΔG . The concept of the G-controlled fatigue algorithm is to perform the testing at a constant energy release rate amplitude ΔG , which is a considerable improvement compared with traditional displacement controlled or load controlled fatigue tests, where fracture mechanism shifts are possible due to a varying energy release rate during the test [1]. When the test is performed with constant displacement amplitude the crack propagates gradually slower as its length increases, resulting in a decrease in energy release rate at the crack tip, due to the increasing leverage and decreasing stiffness of the specimen, a process which continues until the crack ceases to propagate. On the other hand, if the test is performed keeping the load amplitude constant [2] the crack propagates

gradually faster because of the increasing energy release rate at the crack tip until the crack reaches the specimen edge (Fig.1). In both cases the energy release rate varies extensively during the test, and crack kinking into different face/core interface crack paths is possible, resulting in non-consistent crack growth rate measurements.

Fig.1. Testing modes for fatigue crack growth evaluation. Load (P), displacement (D) and energy release rate (G) control modes

In order to perform fatigue testing at constant energy release rate, two different sandwich test configurations are used.

4. The sandwich MMB configuration

The sandwich G-controlled test method is based on the conventional mixed mode bending test method [3] where the specimen is subjected to a combination of mode I and mode II (Fig.2). However, modifications to the kinematic condition have been developed in order to accommodate sandwich specimens with non-negligible shear deformations [4-5]. The sandwich MMB test has earlier been applied for both fracture toughness characterization [6] as well as conventional load and displacement controlled cyclic fatigue characterization [7-8].

Fig.2. MMB test rig and specimen

In order to perform fatigue testing at constant energy release rate, the static face/core interface fracture toughness was initially determined at various mixed mode loadings. Sinusoidal fatigue loading with $R=0.2$ and 2 Hz testing frequency were employed for the study of cyclic crack growth. The fatigue debond length a was monitored and measured visually and also calculated using the compliance (eq.1) and the energy release rate (eq.2) expressions combined with the actual load and displacement data from fatigue tests [5].

$$C_{MMB} = \left[\frac{c}{L} C_{DCB_upper} + \frac{c-L}{2L} C_{DCB_lower} \right] \left[\frac{c}{L} - \alpha \frac{c+L}{2L} \right] + \left(\frac{c+L}{L} \right)^2 C_{CSB} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{MMB} = \frac{P^2}{2b^2} \left[\frac{c}{L} \left(\frac{c}{L} - \alpha \frac{c+L}{2L} \right) \frac{12}{E_f h_f^3} \left[a^2 + 2a\eta^{1/4} + \eta^{1/2} \right] + \left(\frac{c+L}{L} \right)^2 \left(\frac{a^2}{8} \left[\frac{1}{D_{debonded}} - \frac{1}{D_{intact}} \right] \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

The crack length was used to determine the instantly applied energy release rate G , using an advanced control algorithm programmed into the servo-hydraulic controller software. In this control algorithm, the instant value of G applied to the sandwich specimen is compared to the initial energy release rate, G_0 , and if the condition $G=G_0$ is not fulfilled the displacement amplitude applied to the specimen is adjusted instantaneously through the servo-hydraulic control loop.

4. The modified TSD configuration

The original TSD specimen was introduced as a debond test for foam cored sandwich specimens in 1999 by Li and Carlsson [9]. However, experimental test results and analysis at different tilt angles revealed that the phase angle for a typical TSD specimen is quite unaffected by the tilt angle. However, recently it was proven through a parametric finite element analysis that by reinforcing the loaded face sheet by a stiff metal plate, an increased transverse shear load leads to increased root rotation of the crack tip resulting in considerable expansion of the range of phase angles [10]. Design considerations furthermore outlined that the range of mode-mixity phase angles can be further extended by supporting the core at the cracked end of the specimen. Core crushing at the other end of the specimen can be avoided by using pinned links [10]. Thus, the modified TSD specimen (Fig. 3) and test was identified as a viable and promising candidate for improved mixed mode fracture toughness measurements [11], and especially for sandwich systems incorporating stiff cores, for example balsa core material, the modified TSD specimen and test is attractive [12], as no bending action of the specimen is necessary, like for example in the mixed mode bending (MMB) sandwich specimen [4] and test, leading to a quite limited obtainable phase angle range. The modified TSD specimen has however not earlier been applied for fatigue characterization, thus the focus of this study is to show its applicability for such testing.

Fig.3. The modified TSD specimen and test rig.

In order to perform fatigue testing at constant energy release rate (G-controlled testing) using the modified TSD test rig and specimen, the debond length, a , has to be measured in-situ during testing using a newly developed finite element analysis based compliance technique. The crack length, a , is then again in-situ used to determine the cyclic energy release rate amplitude through application of the same finite element model for the modified TSD specimen, presented earlier in [10]. In Fig.4 an example of crack length versus compliance is shown for a given value of tilt angle θ (0° in this case). The compliance of the TSD specimen increases as function of a (eq. 3) and similar compliance expressions can be calculated for other tilt angles.

$$C_{TSD} = -2.88318 * 10^{-7} + 1.043727 * 10^{-3} a + 4.62771 * 10^{-6} a^2 - 3.62501 * 10^{-8} a^3 \quad (3)$$

$$G_{TSD(\theta=0^\circ)} = \frac{P^2}{2b} d \frac{C_{TSD}}{da} \quad (4)$$

The actual energy release rate applied to the sandwich specimen (eq.4) is then continuously compared to the initial energy release rate and adjustments of the load and/or displacement are applied to the specimen following the same mechanism used for the MMB G-controlled fatigue test.

Fig.4. Example of compliance (C) versus crack length (a) for $\theta = 0^\circ$.

5. Conclusions

A methodology for an energy release rate controlled fatigue testing algorithm has been proposed in order to obtain more reliable measurements of the fatigue crack growth rate over a range of mode-mixities. This will allow characterization of fatigue crack growth rates at sandwich face/core interfaces and eliminating uncertainties due to un-controlled crack path jumps. It was also demonstrated how both the sandwich MMB and modified TSD specimens can be used in combination with the G-control algorithm. Finally, through the G-control algorithm it will be made possible to measure reliable fatigue crack growth data to be used as input to residual fatigue life simulations of debond damaged sandwich components. .

References

- [1] A. Quispitupa, C. Berggreen and L.A. Carlsson, "A Methodology to Study Cyclic Debond Growth at Constant Mode-Mixity and Energy Release Rate", *9th International Conference on Sandwich Structures*, June 14-16, Pasadena, California, USA, 2010.
- [2] A. Shipsha, M. Burman and D. Zenkert "Interfacial fatigue crack growth in foam core sandwich structures". *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures*, 22:123-131, 1999.
- [3] J. Reeder and J.H. Crews, "Mixed-mode bending method for delamination testing". *AIAA Journal*, 28(7):1270-1276, 1990.
- [4] A. Quispitupa, C. Berggreen, and L.A. Carlsson, "On the Analysis of the Mixed Mode Bending (MMB) Sandwich Specimen for Debond Fracture Characterization", *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 76(4):594-613, 2009.
- [5] A. Quispitupa, C. Berggreen, and L.A. Carlsson, "Design Analysis of the Mixed Mode Bending Sandwich Specimen", *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials*, 12(2):253-272, 2010.
- [6] A. Quispitupa, C. Berggreen and L.A. Carlsson, "Face/Core Interface Fracture Characterization of Mixed Mode Bending Sandwich Specimens", *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures*, in press, 2011.
- [7] A. Quispitupa, C. Berggreen and L.A. Carlsson, "Fatigue debond growth in sandwich structures loaded in mixed mode bending". *13th European Conference in Composite Materials*, 2-5 June Stockholm, Sweden, 2008.
- [8] A. Quispitupa, C. Berggreen, M. Manca and L.A. Carlsson, "Mixed Mode Face/Core Interface Fatigue Crack Propagation in Sandwich Composites", *16th International Conference on Composite Structures*, 28-30 June, Porto, Portugal, 2011.
- [9] X. Li and L.A. Carlsson, "The tilted sandwich debond (TSD) specimen for face/core interface fracture characterization", *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials*, 1:60-75, 1999
- [10] C. Berggreen and L.A. Carlsson, "A Modified TSD Specimen for Fracture Toughness Characterization – Fracture Mechanics Analysis and Design", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 44(15):1893-1912, 2010.
- [11] C. Berggreen, A. Quispitupa, J.L. Alonso and L.A. Carlsson, "Experimental Fracture Toughness Characterization Using the Modified TSD Specimen", *9th International Conference on Sandwich Structures*, June 14-16, Pasadena, California, USA, 2010.
- [12] A. Quispitupa and C. Berggreen, "Face/Core Debond Fracture Characterization of Balsa Wood Sandwich Composites", *18th International Conference on Composite Materials*, August 21-26, Jeju, Korea, 2011, submitted.